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Biotransformation of anthelmintics in nematodes in relation to drug resistance

Ondřej Vosála^a, Josef Krátký^a ,
Lucie Raisová Stuchlíková^a

^a Department of Biochemical Sciences, Charles University in Prague, Faculty of Pharmacy, Heyrovského 1203, Hradec Králové, CZ-500 05, Czech Republic

^b Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Charles University in Prague, Faculty of Pharmacy, Heyrovského 1203, Hradec Králové, CZ-500 05, Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

In all organisms, the biotransformation of xenobiotics to less toxic and more hydrophilic compounds represents an effective defense strategy. In pathogens, the biotransformation of drugs (used for their elimination from the host) may provide undesirable protective effects that could potentially compromise the drug's efficacy. Accordingly, increased drug deactivation via accelerated biotransformation is now considered as one of the mechanisms of drug resistance. The present study summarizes the current knowledge regarding the biotransformation of anthelmintics, specifically drugs used to treat mainly nematodes, a group of parasites that are a significant health concern for humans and animals. The main biotransformation enzymes are introduced and their roles in anthelmintic metabolism in nematodes are discussed with a particular focus on their potential participation in drug resistance. Similarly, the inducibility of biotransformation enzymes with sublethal doses of anthelmintics is presented in view of its potential contribution to drug resistance development. In the conclusion, the main tasks awaiting scientists in this area are outlined.

1. Introduction

1.1. Introduction to nematodes

Parasitic nematodes are the most prevalent helminth group of both humans (CDC, 2024) and livestock worldwide (Kaur et al., 2017; Saemi Soudkolaei et al., 2021; Abbas et al., 2022; Cai et al., 2023; Merlin et al., 2024). Approximately 120 genera of parasitic nematodes are known to infect humans and livestock. Given that number, a high variability in biology and life strategies is to be expected. Although the most prevalent genera of parasitic nematodes have direct lifecycles (e.g., pinworms, hookworms, trichostrongylids; also known as “soil-transmitted helminths” or “geohelminths” (Ransome, 1906; Bass, 1910; Madsen, 1945)), many others utilise intermediate hosts such as annelids (*Metastrongylus* spp. (Schwartz and Alicata, 1934; Rose, 1959); gastropods (*Angiostrongylus* spp. (Lim and Heyneman, 1965; Mozzer et al., 2015); crustaceans (*Dracunculus* spp. (Fedchenko, 1971; Yelifari et al., 2016); insect (*Habronema* spp. (Ransom, 1911; Traversa et al., 2008) or *Loa loa* (Leipert, 1913; Ndzeshang et al., 2020)), and many other taxa (e.g., cephalopods for *Contraecaecum* spp. (Norris and Overstreet, 1976; Shamsi, 2019); as well as a wide spectrum of both vertebrate and invertebrate paratenic hosts (e.g., earthworms for *Syngamus trachea* (Walker, 1886; Clapham, 2009) or small mammals for *Toxocara canis*

(Höppli, 1923; Dubinský et al., 1995)).

The adults of veterinary and medicinally important genera of nematodes are primarily located in the gastrointestinal tract (e.g., ascarids, pinworms, hookworms, whipworms or trichostrongylids (Ransome, 1906; Bass, 1910; Madsen, 1945; Miller, 1947; Schacher, 1957), yet other localizations such as lungs (*Metastrongylus* spp., *Syngamus* spp. (Dunn and White, 1954; Fernando et al., 1971)), lymphatic system (*Wuchereria bancrofti*, *Brugia* spp., (Rao Sundar, 1930; Chirgwin et al., 2006), connective tissue (*Onchocerca* spp., *Dirofilaria repens* (Webber and Hawking, 1955; Mellor, 1973)), urinary system (*Dictyophyme renale*, *Capillaria plica* (Senior et al., 1980)), eyes (*Thelazia* spp., *Oxyuris mansonii* (Fielding, 1927), muscles (*Haycocknema perplexum* (Spratt et al., 1999) or central nervous system (*Elaphostrongylus cervi*, *Menigonema peruzzii* (Boussinesq et al., 1995; Handeland et al., 2000) are also observed. In some cases, the somatic migration or encapsulation of larval stages represents a substantial pathological aspect of infection, e.g., neural larva migrans, parenteral trichinellosis, and habronemiasis (Frothingham, 1906; Irvine and Irvine, 1959; Huff et al., 1984; Anderson, 2000; Yarmut et al., 2008).

Given that the infection by nematodes negatively impacts billions of people and livestock production (Merlin et al., 2024), the physiology and biochemistry of nematodes have been intensively studied, driven by the need for effective tools to combat them. *Haemonchus contortus*, an

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: lenka.skalova@faf.cuni.cz (L. Skálová).

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intestinal pathogen of artiodactyls is by far the most researched model for parasitic nematodes (Gilleard, 2013; Kotze and Prichard, 2016; Rychlá et al., 2024). To reduce the ethical and financial challenges associated with studying human and livestock pathogens, many rodent-infecting nematode species are used as model organisms to investigate various aspects of nematodiasis *in vivo* (Poulin, 2023). The primary role as a model species is played by *Heligmosomoides polygyrus*, a monoxenic intestinal parasite of rodents (Precious and Barrett, 1989; Ghorbani et al., 2023; Stevens et al., 2023; Firmanty et al., 2024). Other such species include *Trichuris muris*, a model for whipworm infections (Bay et al., 2023), *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis*, a rodent hookworm (Ferguson et al., 2023), *Strongyloides ratti* alternating between free-living and parasitic stages (Shaikh et al., 2023), or model filaria *Litosomoides sigmodontis* (Stevens et al., 2023, 2024). Nevertheless, the free-living nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans* remains the most studied model organism (Hahnel et al., 2020).

1.2. Introduction to antinematodal drugs

The current chemical control of nematodes relies on a restricted number of anthelmintic drug classes, most of which were introduced before 2000. These well-established or “old” anthelmintics include macrocyclic lactones, benzimidazoles, imidazothiazoles, tetrahydropyrimidines, halogenated salicylanilides, and several other minor classes with specific uses. Since then, only three novel classes have been introduced to the market in veterinary medicine: aminoacetonitrile derivatives, spiroindoles, and octadepsipeptides (Nixon et al., 2020). While the old drugs are well-established worldwide, with a broad spectrum of host species, the new drug classes still have only limited use. Unfortunately, the limited number of currently available anthelmintics, coupled with their long period of use, create a favorable environment for the emergence of anthelmintic resistance (Fissiha and Kinde, 2021).

The aforementioned drug classes can be divided into several subgroups according to their mechanism of action. Most currently used anthelmintic classes target the nematodes’ nervous and muscle tissue through various mechanisms interacting with different types of receptors and ion channels. However, there are exceptions, such as benzimidazoles directly affecting microtubule formation in cells and salicylanilides that uncouple oxidative phosphorylation in the mitochondria (Martin, 1997; Abongwa et al., 2017).

Macrocyclic lactones and benzimidazoles are currently the most widely used anthelmintics in the world. Benzimidazoles have been on the market for a longer period of time than other anthelmintics, as the first benzimidazole drug, thiabendazole (TBZ), was introduced in 1961, over 60 years ago. Subsequently, a number of more efficacious successors were developed, including albendazole, fenbendazole, flubendazole, mebendazole, ricobendazole, oxibendazole, triclabendazole, and two prodrugs febantel and netobimin. They are of significant importance in both veterinary and human medicine (Cook, 1990). Benzimidazoles can be considered true broad-spectrum anthelmintics as they act not only on the nematodes but some members also on cestodes and trematodes (Prichard, 1988; Lacey, 1990). In parasite cells, they selectively bind to the β -tubulin, thereby inhibiting microtubule formation and ultimately leading to the destruction of the cell structure and the subsequent death of the parasite (Lacey, 1990; Abongwa et al., 2017).

Macrocyclic lactones were first introduced to the market in 1981. They primarily act on nematodes but also have important activity against the ectoparasites (Campbell et al., 1983; Shoop et al., 1995). Currently, abamectin, doramectin, eprinomectin, ivermectin, selamectin (sub-group of avermectins), milbemycin oxime, and moxidectin (sub-group of milbemycins) are in use in a broad spectrum of indications in both animals and humans (Nixon et al., 2020). They act as agonists on the glutamate-gated chloride channels of the nematodes, inhibiting movement and pharyngeal pumping. Except for the primary mechanism of action, the avermectins also act as antagonists on GABA-activated channels and nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) on somatic

muscle cells (Abongwa et al., 2017).

The smaller yet no less significant classes of anthelmintics include imidazothiazoles and tetrahydropyrimidines. Although they are structurally distinct, these compounds share a similar mechanism of action, acting as agonists on nAChRs in nematodes on body wall muscles and causing spastic paralysis of the worm. The sole imidazothiazole currently available on the market is levamisole, an L-isomer of tetramisole. The tetrahydropyrimidine class includes pyrantel, oxantel, and morantel (Martin, 1997; Abongwa et al., 2017). Both groups are used in veterinary and human medicine (Vokrál et al., 2023). The latest addition to drugs acting on nAChRs is tribendimidine, a drug approved in China in 2004 and currently used solely for treating nematode and trematode infections in humans (Hu et al., 2009).

Only two members of halogenated salicylanilides, closantel and raxofaxanide, that are used in veterinary medicine have demonstrated efficacy against blood-feeding and filarial nematodes only. Moreover, they are also active against trematodes and ectoparasites (Guerrero, 1984; Swan, 1999; Segura-Cabrera et al., 2011). They act as proton ionophores and selectively uncouple oxidative phosphorylation in parasite mitochondria (Martin, 1997).

The most recent additions to the drugs employed in the treatment of nematodes are octadepsipeptides (emodepside), aminoacetonitrile derivatives (monepantel, MPTL), and spiroindoles (derquantel) (Nixon et al., 2020). Each group has only one member currently available on the market. Emodepside acts on the calcium-activated potassium channel (SLO-1) and latrophilin receptor (LAT-1) of nematodes, inhibiting pharyngeal pumping, paralysis, and death. It is currently approved for use in dogs and cats in combination with praziquantel; however, treating human soil-transmitted helminthiasis is also of interest (Epe and Kaminsky, 2013; Montresor and Gabrielli, 2023). MPTL acts as an allosteric modulator and agonist on the nematode-specific DEG-3 subfamily of nAChRs, causing muscle cell depolarization and paralysis. At present, it is used only in sheep (Epe and Kaminsky, 2013; Abongwa et al., 2017). The last addition to the nematocidal drugs is derquantel, which was introduced to the market in 2010. Derquantel acts as an antagonist of nAChRs in nematodes, causing flaccid paralysis. It is now used in combination with abamectin to treat various nematodes in sheep (Epe and Kaminsky, 2013).

2. Drug resistance in nematodes

The term “resistance” was originally coined to describe the ability of a population to tolerate a drug to a greater extent than would be expected in a normal population of the same species. The term “drug resistance” is defined as a reduction in the effectiveness of a previously effective drug based on the acquired ability of pathogens to tolerate a previously lethal drug. Since the 1980s, the concept of resistance has been further delineated in the context of specific terms, including cross-resistance, and multidrug resistance, which are now becoming increasingly relevant (Prichard et al., 1980; Kotze and Prichard, 2016). Subsequently, these definitions have been updated considering the requirements of the World Association for the Advancement of Veterinary Parasitology (Coles et al., 1992).

Almost all pathogens, including parasitic nematodes, can defend themselves and develop drug resistance. As mentioned above regarding nematodes, variety in life histories, a vast range of definitive hosts (WHO, 2021), switching between sylvatic and urban life cycles, and potential for zoonotic transmission (Jori et al., 2021; Agustina et al., 2022) in combination with irresponsible suboptimal treatment of infections (van Wyk, 2001) and/or frequent and repeated usage of the same drugs (WHO, 2021) led to widespread emergence of anthelmintic resistance in the last decades, which was already highlighted by Kaplan et al., in 2004 (Kaplan, 2004).

The resistance of nematodes to anthelmintics has been observed in many hosts, with the most prevalent cases occurring in sheep, cattle, horses, and dogs. The highest rates of resistance have been observed in

H. contortus, *Teladorsagia circumcincta* and *Trichostrongylus* spp. (Gilleard and Redman, 2016; Sangster et al., 2018). Nematodes have demonstrated the ability to develop resistance to the majority of anthelmintics employed. The first case of resistance to TBZ (introduced to the market in 1961) was documented in 1964. Subsequently, resistance to the imidothiazole group emerged in 1979 (introduced in 1970) and the macrocyclic lactones in 1988 (introduced in 1981). The resistance to the most recently introduced anthelmintic MPTL (2010) was already reported in 2013 (Mederos et al., 2014). It is obvious that resistance even to new anthelmintics will be inevitable unless the drug is designed in such a way that nematodes are unable to develop resistance to it. Nevertheless, this requires a comprehensive understanding of the resistance mechanisms and all factors that contribute to the development of resistance in nematodes (Mukherjee et al., 2023; Cai et al., 2024; Lespine et al., 2024).

Generally, drug resistance can be based on alterations in drug targets, enhanced repair of drug-evoked damages, increased drug efflux, or enhanced drug deactivation via biotransformation (Harder, 2016; Kotze and Prichard, 2016). The target site mechanism of resistance in nematodes is well-documented for benzimidazole anthelmintics since several alterations in the primary target, β -tubulin isotype I, were reported. In *H. contortus*, a single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) from TTC to TAC in codon 200 has been observed, resulting in a tyrosine-phenylalanine substitution (Walsh et al., 2007; von Samson-Himmelstjerna et al., 2009). This alteration has been linked to a reduced affinity of benzimidazoles for β -tubulin. Interestingly, the same “mutation” also occurs naturally in *Fasciola hepatica*, which explains its natural tolerance to most benzimidazole drugs (Fairweather et al., 2020). Additionally, SNPs in other codons, specifically 167 and 198, have been identified as contributing to benzimidazole resistance (Barrere et al., 2012; Kotze et al., 2012; Sangster et al., 2018).

The imidazothiazoles (e.g. levamisole) act as agonists of the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR), mimicking the function of acetylcholine, which results in spastic paralysis of nematodes. In *H. contortus*, the nAChR consists of four subunits UNC-29, UNC-38, UNC-63 and ACR-8, one of which is repeated, enabling the overall structure to form a pentamer. A change in the expression or structure of a subunit can lead to the development of resistance to levamisole (Kotze et al., 2014). In *H. contortus*, the shortened genes *unc-63* and *acr-8* are associated with reduced sensitivity to levamisole. Additionally, reduced expression of *unc-63a* and *unc-29* was found in resistant isolates (R-isolates) than in a sensitive isolate (S-isolate) (Sarai et al., 2014). Recent studies showed no association of levamisole resistance with altered expression of *acr-8* (Baltrusis et al., 2021; Doyle et al., 2022) and suggested non-synonymous mutation AGC→ACC (codon position 168-S168T) in *acr-8* gene as a key determinant of levamisole resistance in *H. contortus* (Antonopoulos et al., 2022; Doyle et al., 2022). The nAChR, specifically the ACR-23 subunit, represents the MPTL target in nematodes. In *C. elegans* with a mutation in the *acr-23* gene, tolerance to MPTL has been observed (Fru and Puoti, 2014; Niciura et al., 2019). In *H. contortus* resistant to MPTL, a number of mutations in the drug target gene (*Hco-mptl-1*) that would most-likely result in a non-functional receptor was detected (Bagnall et al., 2017). Concerning ivermectin (IVM), mutations of the genes for glutamate-gated chloride channels (*glc-1*, *avr-14*, *avr-15*) in *C. elegans* might be responsible for nematode resistance. However, it has been demonstrated that the mutation of all three genes is necessary for the development of robust resistance in *C. elegans* (Dent et al., 2000) and none appear to be relevant for resistance in *H. contortus*.

In addition to target-site mechanisms, non-target-site mechanisms are involved in anthelmintic resistance in nematodes. Among these mechanisms, the increased efflux of anthelmintics based on increased expression of efflux transporters, namely P-glycoproteins, has been mostly studied, particularly in the association with IVM-resistance (Dent et al., 2000; Godoy et al., 2015). However, over the past decade, the association of increased anthelmintic deactivation via increased expression of biotransformation enzymes and nematode resistance to

anthelmintics has been clearly demonstrated. The following sections summarize current knowledge about anthelmintic biotransformation in nematodes and the enzymes responsible.

3. Metabolism of anthelmintics in nematodes

The biotransformation of anthelmintics consists of two classical phases: phase I reactions, in which polar functional groups are introduced or uncovered by oxidation, reduction or hydrolysis, and phase II reactions, in which the parent drug and/or its metabolites are conjugated with endogenous molecules such as glucose to increase their water solubility and facilitate excretion. Understanding the metabolism of anthelmintics and the responsible enzymes in both hosts and nematodes is essential to ensure the safety of host therapy, to assess the risk of drug-drug interactions and to minimize the development of drug resistance.

The most recent release (WBPS19) of the WormBase/Parasite database (<https://parasite.wormbase.org> (Howe et al., 2017),) was mined via the BioMart tool search, using an InterPro domain of the most important biotransformation enzymes, namely cytochromes P450 (CYPs), glutathione-S-transferases (GST), short-chain dehydrogenases (SDRs), aldo-keto reductases (AKRs), and UDP-glycosyltransferases (UGTs). A number of well-annotated genomes were explored in order to encompass all nematode clades of the most significant parasites (Table 1). Further details on these enzymes, their relation to resistance and involvement in anthelmintic deactivation can be found in the respective sections below.

Concerning anthelmintic biotransformation in nematodes, albendazole (ABZ) represents the most extensively studied benzimidazole drug. In the initial study, only three ABZ metabolites, formed by S-oxidation and glycosylation, were identified in *H. contortus* adults exposed to ABZ (Cvilink et al., 2008b). A more recent study analyzed ABZ metabolism separately in adult females and males of *H. contortus* from a S-isolate and R-isolates. Many new ABZ metabolites were identified (Fig. 1), some of which revealed novel biotransformation reactions in nematodes e.g. hydrolysis of carbamate side chain, which was not detected using less sensitive analytical instrumentation (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018). The results also demonstrated significant sex and strain differences in ABZ biotransformation where, the higher amount of ABZ metabolites formed in R-than in S-isolates indicates that anthelmintic metabolism may play a role in drug resistance. Stasiuk et al. (2019) provided confirmation of ABZ oxidation and glycosylation in *H. contortus* (Stasiuk et al., 2019). Interestingly, *H. contortus* eggs and larvae were also observed to metabolize ABZ via oxidation, glycosylation and acetylation (only in eggs) (Kellerová et al., 2020a). In contrast, *Ascaris lumbricoides/suum* was found to metabolize ABZ only via oxidation, while the free-living nematode *C. elegans* is capable of both ABZ oxidation and glycosylation (Solana et al., 2001; Laing et al., 2010; Stasiuk et al., 2019). Seven metabolites of ABZ-sulphoxide (ricobendazole) were identified in *H. contortus* adults (via second S-oxidation, S-oxide reduction and N-glycosylation) (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018).

The initial study of the biotransformation of flubendazole (FLU) in *H. contortus* adults, revealed the formation of three metabolites via carbonyl reduction (FLU-R) and glycosylation (FLU-glycoside and FLU-R-glycoside) (Cvilink et al., 2008a, 2008b). Subsequent studies compared the metabolism of FLU in *H. contortus* adults from four different strains (drug-susceptible, IVM-resistant, benzimidazole-resistant and multidrug-resistant strain) and demonstrated increased FLU reduction and glycosylation in resistant nematodes (Vokřál et al., 2012). Furthermore, *H. contortus* females were more active in FLU reduction than males (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018; Rychlá et al., 2024). The recent study of FLU biotransformation in *H. contortus* adults identified eight new metabolites (Fig. 2), four of which are formed via new biotransformation reactions, namely carbamate hydrolysis, hydroxylation, methylation and acetylation (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018). All developmental stages of *H. contortus* can deactivate FLU via FLU reduction, however, only minimal quantities of FLU-R were detected in

Table 1

Summary of genes encoding biotransformation enzymes in helminth genomes from WormBase/ParaSite (Howe et al., 2017).

Species	Clade	Genome Project	Genome size [Mbp]	CYPs	GSTs	AKRs	SDRs	UGTs
<i>Angiostrongylus vasorum</i>	V	PRJNA663250	280	22	19	14	37	15
<i>Ascaris suum</i>	III	PRJNA62057	298	18	27	10	49	31
<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	V	PRJNA13758	100	79	75	14	78	71
<i>Cylicocyclus nassatus</i>	V	PRJEB63274	515	40	41	31	84	57
<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	V	PRJEB506	283	28	35	20	47	36
<i>Necator americanus</i>	V	PRJNA1007425	234	37	31	18	57	44
<i>Strongyloides stercoralis</i>	IV	PRJNA930454	44	21	14	5	43	34
<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	I	PRJNA12603	64	6	11	2	25	4
<i>Trichuris suis</i>	I	PRJNA179528	64	13	11	4	27	13
<i>Trichuris trichiura</i>	I	PRJEB535	81	13	11	12	29	14

Abbreviations: cytochromes P450 (CYPs), glutathione-S-transferases (GST), short-chain dehydrogenases (SDRs), aldo-keto reductases (AKRs), and UDP-glycosyltransferases (UGTs).

Fig. 1. Proposed metabolic pathway of albendazole (ABZ) in *H. contortus* adults (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018).

eggs and larvae (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018; Rychlá et al., 2024). Similarly, the structural analogue mebendazole (MBZ) was also metabolized via carbonyl reduction and glycosylation in *H. contortus* and *C. elegans* (Stasiuk et al., 2019). In contrast, only the reduction of the MBZ carbonyl group was observed in *A. lumbricoides/suum* (Kohler and Bachmann, 1981).

The metabolism of other therapeutically important benzimidazoles, including fenbendazole and oxfendazole consists mainly of glycosylation as the predominant biotransformation pathway in *H. contortus* and *C. elegans*. In contrast, TBZ was not metabolized in *H. contortus* at all (Stasiuk et al., 2019).

In addition to benzimidazoles, the biotransformation of anthelmintics from other classes has also been investigated. In *H. contortus* adults, MPTL, the only representative of amino acetonitrile derivatives, was metabolized via oxidation, and hydrolysis, but no second-phase biotransformation products were detected. In addition, *H. contortus* adults from R-isolates were able to form a greater number of MPTL metabolites than those from a S-isolate (Stuchlíková et al., 2014). Apparently macrocyclic lactones are metabolized to a lesser extent by

H. contortus adults, as only hydroxylated moxidectin (MXD) was detected (Alvinerie et al., 2001), and no metabolite was found for IVM (Alvinerie et al., 2001; Vokřál et al., 2013). Ecdysteroids (ECD) were glycosylated by *A. lumbricoides/suum* and *P. equorum* (O'Hanlon et al., 1987; O'Hanlon et al., 1991). Nevertheless, it is conceivable that additional metabolites may be identified using current analytical instrumentation, as evidenced by the identification of novel metabolites in the case of ABZ or FLU.

The individual steps of biotransformation of all anthelmintics studied in nematodes are summarized in Table 2.

4. Phase I biotransformation enzymes

4.1. Cytochromes P450

Cytochromes P450 (CYPs) represent a superfamily of ubiquitous hem-thiolate proteins, characterized by an apoprotein with iron-protoporphyrin IX in the active site and peculiar position of the Soret peak of complex Fe(II)-CO at wavelength 450 nm. CYPs are known

Fig. 2. Proposed metabolic pathway of flubendazole (FLU) in *H. contortus* adults (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018).

mainly for their monooxygenase function, which exhibits a broad substrate specificity, ranging from endogenous to various xenobiotic substrates (Larigot et al., 2022; Lim et al., 2022). The reaction is carried out in the presence of a cofactor – NADPH or NADH, which provides the necessary electrons for catalytic action, the electron transfer from the cofactor is then ensured by an enzyme, flavoprotein – NADPH-CYP-reductase. Besides monooxygenase, such as hydroxylase or epoxidase, CYPs can act as peroxidases and reductases as well (Hartman et al., 2021; Larigot et al., 2022; Lim et al., 2022).

CYPs are found in all living organisms, including animals, plants, fungi, bacteria, and viruses. In humans, there are 57 functional CYPs, which are classified into 18 families and 43 subfamilies. Concerning metabolism of xenobiotics, families 1–4 comprising 18 members localized in the endoplasmic reticulum are the most important. The CYP1, 2 and 3 families are crucial for drug metabolism, as they metabolize up to 80 % of clinical drugs (Zhao et al., 2021; Lim et al., 2022).

In the free-living nematode *C. elegans*, CYPs play a critical role in xenobiotic metabolism (Larigot et al., 2022; Lim et al., 2022). The genome of *C. elegans* contains 80 genes encoding CYPs, including 4 xenobiotic-inducible enzyme families: CYP31, CYP33, CYP34 and CYP35 (Menzel et al., 2001, 2005). Several studies have demonstrated that many CYPs can be induced in *C. elegans* adult worms following exposure to various xenobiotic compounds, such as caffeine, ethanol, rifampicin, phenobarbital, ethidium bromide, various pesticides like glyphosates, paraquat, DDT or TBZ, as well as different metal ions such as zinc, copper, aluminium, or cadmium (Menzel et al., 2001; Min et al., 2015; Patananan et al., 2015; Larigot et al., 2022). A number of studies have reported a correlation between the silencing or knock-down of certain CYP genes and subsequent effects on a range of physiological functions in *C. elegans*. For example, the knock-down of CYP22A1 affected adult worm life span, morphology, embryonic development, larval development, dauer formation and lipid metabolism. However,

only a few CYP-catalyzed reactions involved in endogenous metabolism e.g., the epoxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids, epoxidation and hydroxylation of amino acids, or oxidation of cholesten-3-ones, have been described in *C. elegans* (Kulas et al., 2008; Kosel et al., 2011; Keller et al., 2014; Larigot et al., 2022).

The genome of the parasitic nematode *H. contortus* contains the orthologs of the CYP34 and CYP35 involved in xenobiotic metabolism in *C. elegans*. However, it is possible that *H. contortus* lacks a typical CYP subfamily involved in endogenous metabolism (Laing et al., 2015; Kellerová et al., 2019). Low CYP activities toward xenobiotics were detected in *H. larvae* and strong inducibility of these activities by phenobarbital was demonstrated (Kotze, 1997). The expression of CYPs genes in *H. contortus* has been documented in several studies (Kellerová et al., 2019; Larigot et al., 2022; Lim et al., 2022), however, the majority of CYPs have only been characterized at the mRNA expression level. This is due to the limited availability of antibodies for the detection available for the majority of *H. contortus* proteins and scarce proteomic reports, which may be problematic as some CYPs isoforms are regulated by post-transcriptional modifications, which means that mRNA levels do not necessarily reflect protein expression or activity (Sumida et al., 1999; Hartman et al., 2021).

A recent study investigated the potential role of CYPs in resistance of *H. contortus* to IVM (Kellerová et al., 2019). Expression levels of different CYP genes after exposure of adult worms of *H. contortus* to IVM in various concentrations were compared. The upregulation of *cyp-5* in females, and *cyp-3* and *cyp-6* in males was observed, indicating a potential role for these genes in the development of resistance in *H. contortus* (Kellerová et al., 2019; Kellerová et al., 2020). The activity of CYP was observed in the larvae of *Trichostrongylus colubriformis* and *Turbatrix aceti*, with a probable role in metabolism of eobiotics rather than xenobiotics (Barrett, 1998; Kotze et al., 2006). In contrast, a single CYP plays an essential role in the endogenous metabolism of cholesterol

Table 2

The biotransformation reactions of anthelmintics in nematodes.

Biotransformation	Anthelmintics	Nematode	References
Phase I			
Oxidation	MPTL, ABZ, RCB ABZ, FBZ, TBZ ABZ	<i>H. contortus</i> <i>C. elegans</i> <i>A. suum</i>	(Cvilink et al., 2008b; Kellerová et al., 2020a; Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018; Stasiuk et al., 2019; Stuchlíková et al., 2014; Vokřál et al., 2013) (Laing et al., 2010; Stasiuk et al., 2019) (Solana et al., 2001)
Hydroxylation	MPTL, FLU, MXD	<i>H. contortus</i>	(Alvinerie et al., 2001; Kellerová et al., 2020b; Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018; Stuchlíková et al., 2014)
Reduction of carbonyl group	FLU MBZ	<i>H. contortus</i> <i>A. suum</i>	(Cvilink et al., 2008a,b; Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018; Rychlá et al., 2024; Vokřál et al., 2012) (Kohler and Bachmann, 1981)
Hydrolysis	MBZ, TBZ, OxBZ MPTL, FLU, ABZ MBZ	<i>C. elegans</i> <i>H. contortus</i> <i>A. suum</i>	Stasiuk et al. (2019) (Kellerová et al., 2020b; Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018; Stuchlíková et al., 2014) (Kohler and Bachmann, 1981)
Reduction of sulfoxide	RCB	<i>H. contortus</i>	(Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018)
Phase II			
Methylation	FLU	<i>H. contortus</i>	(Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018)
O-acetylation	FLU, ABZ	<i>H. contortus</i>	((Kellerová et al., 2020a; Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018)
O-/N-Glycosylation	FLU, ABZ, RCB ABZ, FBZ, MBZ, TBZ, OxBZ ECD	<i>H. contortus</i> , <i>C. elegans</i> <i>A. suum</i> , <i>P. equorum</i>	(Cvilink et al., 2008b; Kellerová et al., 2020a; Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018; Vokřál et al., 2012, 2013) (Laing et al., 2010; Stasiuk et al., 2019) (O'Hanlon et al., 1991; O'Hanlon et al., 1987)

Abbreviations: albendazole (ABZ), ecdysteroids (ECD), fenbendazole (FBZ), flubendazole (FLU), mebendazole (MBZ), monepantel (MPTL), moxidectin (MDX), oxfendazole (oxBZ), ricobendazole (RCB) thiabendazole (TBZ).

and steroid hormones in trematodes *Schistosoma mansoni* and *S. haematobium* (Saeed et al., 2002; Ziniel et al., 2015).

4.2. Other oxidases of xenobiotics in nematodes

CYPs are the most important xenobiotic-oxidizing enzymes in *C. elegans*, but their relevance is unclear in parasitic nematodes as described above. Besides CYPs, several other enzymes can also oxidize xenobiotics. In mammals, flavin-containing monooxygenases (FMOs) are among the most active enzymes catalyzing detoxification of many xenobiotics via the oxidative pathway. The conserved and ancient FMO family consists of FAD-, NADPH- and O₂-dependent enzymes that catalyze the oxygenation of nucleophilic heteroatom centers in a variety of substrates. The *C. elegans* genome contains 5 predicted genes encoding putative homologues of mammalian FMOs, which have been named *fmo* and numbered *fmo-1* to *fmo-5*. Similar orthologues have been identified in the related nematode *C. briggsae* (Petalcorin et al., 2005). Although FMOs are usually classified as xenobiotic-metabolizing enzymes, they

also metabolize specific endogenous substrates as part of a discrete physiological process. In *C. elegans*, *fmo-2* gene expression was significantly induced by silver nanoparticle exposure (Eom et al., 2013). *Fmo-2* was a highly upregulated gene in *C. elegans* infected with the bacterium *Enterococcus faecalis* (Dasgupta et al., 2020), and the expression of this gene was also activated by dietary restriction and was associated with lifespan extension (Leiser et al., 2015; Beydoun et al., 2023). Inactivation of *fmo-4* resulted in dramatic hypoosmotic hypersensitivity (Hirani et al., 2016). Despite a great importance of FMO in the model nematode *C. elegans*, no information is available on FMO in parasitic nematodes.

In plants and bacteria, peroxidases are important oxidases that detoxify many xenobiotics, including environmental pollutants (Durán and Esposito, 2000; Kumar and Arora, 2022). Peroxidases also play an irreplaceable role in the free-living nematode *C. elegans*, but mainly as antioxidant enzymes (Thein et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2021). In the entomopathogenic nematode *Steinernema hermaphroditum*, the peroxidase gene *skpo-2* controls body size (Schwartz et al., 2023). Peroxidases are among the proteins identified in the excretory/secretory products of the adults of *Cooperia oncophora* (Borloo et al., 2013) and *Teladorsagia circumcincta* (Craig et al., 2006), which suggests their role in defense against the host immune system. Microsomes from *H. contortus* adults demonstrated potassium ferrocyanide peroxidase activity using cumene hydroperoxide (Kotze, 1999). However, it remains uncertain whether nematode peroxidases are capable of oxidizing xenobiotics *in vivo*.

Alcohol dehydrogenases (ADH) and aldehyde dehydrogenases (ALDH) are enzymes that catalyze the oxidation of alcohols and aldehydes, respectively. In *C. elegans*, the activities of ADH towards ethanol and other α,β -unsaturated alcohols have been observed (Alaimo et al., 2012; Saleem et al., 2023). The induction of ADH and ALDH in *Panagrellus redivivus* following exposure to various alcohols was reported, along with the effective NADH/NADPH-linked reduction of aldehydes (Kriger et al., 1977). Likewise, *H. contortus* demonstrated the capacity to oxidize aldehydes via NAD/NADP-linked systems (Brophy and Barrett, 1990).

4.3. Reductases of xenobiotics

In addition to oxidases, reductases are also involved in the Phase I of xenobiotic biotransformation (Jin and Penning, 2007). Reductive biotransformation is generally less prevalent than oxidative biotransformation, but reduction represents the primary deactivation pathway for certain compounds, e.g. carbonyl-containing compounds. Reductases of carbonyls protect organisms from the toxic effects of reactive xenobiotic compounds, and also metabolizes a number of endogenous substances (Cvilink et al., 2008a, 2009a).

Carbonyl-reducing enzymes are NAD(P)H-dependent enzymes that are present in all genomes, from simple microorganisms to higher eukaryotes (Barski et al., 2008; Persson et al., 2009). These enzymes are classified into three superfamilies, namely medium-chain dehydrogenases (MDRs), short-chain dehydrogenases (SDRs) and aldo-keto reductases (AKRs), according to their primary structure and conserved motifs (Jez and Penning, 2001). The substrate specificity of carbonyl-reducing enzymes is broad and overlapping. Consequently, a single compound may serve as a substrate for multiple enzymes from different superfamilies (Munir and Barrett, 1985; Oppermann, 2007; Barski et al., 2008). On the other hand, most of these enzymes catalyze stereospecific reduction, whereby a specific reductase generates a fixed ratio of each enantiomer of the product. Furthermore, if the substrate is chiral, the enzyme may exhibit stereoselectivity, reducing only one stereoisomer (Škarydová et al., 2010). The majority of reductive enzymes are localized in the cytosol, although some members are found in the membranes of the endoplasmic reticulum, the mitochondria or peroxisomes (Oppermann, 2007; Barski et al., 2008).

In humans, the SDR superfamily comprises over 70 enzymes, many of which are membrane-bound (Bray et al., 2009; Persson et al., 2009). Most members exhibit low pairwise sequence identity; however, they

share common sequence motifs defining the cofactor binding site (TGxxxGxG) and the catalytic tetrad with highly conserved amino acids (Tyr, Lys, Asn, Ser). In contrast, the substrate recognition site is highly variable between individual members, allowing for a broad substrate acceptance (Persson et al., 2009; Beck et al., 2017; Kisiela et al., 2018). MDRs constitute a large enzyme superfamily with more than 1000 members, further subdivided into several families (Persson et al., 1994; Jörnvall et al., 1999). The most extensively studied are the alcohol dehydrogenases, which are responsible for the detoxification of alcohols, aldehydes and the metabolism of bile acids (Jörnvall et al., 2000; Marschall et al., 2000). Other families include the enzymes polyol dehydrogenases, quinone oxidoreductases, mitochondrial respiratory function proteins, acyl-CoA reductases and leukotriene B4 dehydrogenases (Nordling et al., 2002). AKRs are predominantly monomeric soluble proteins with a broad substrate specificity. They share a common conserved (β/α)₈ barrel structure and a conserved pyridine nucleotide binding site (Barski et al., 2008; Penning, 2015).

There is limited information on carbonyl reductases in parasitic nematodes, although they certainly play an important role in their lives, particularly in the metabolism of anthelmintics. The reduction of carbonyl-containing compounds and/or carbonyl-reducing enzymes have been studied in *T. circumcincta*, *B. malayi*, *C. elegans*, *H. contortus*, *Globodera pallida* and *A. lumbricoides/sum* (Kohler and Bachmann, 1981; Brophy et al., 2012; Matoušková et al., 2016). Reductase activity towards several model substrates (D-L-glyceraldehyde, daunorubicin, acenaphthenol, metyrapone, oracin) was detected in the subcellular fractions of *H. contortus* and the enzyme activities observed were similar to those found in farm animals (Szoťáková et al., 2004; Cvilink et al., 2008a). Furthermore, the ability of *H. contortus* to reduce the carbonyl group of the anthelmintic drugs FLU and MBZ has been confirmed (Vokřál et al., 2012; Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018). All developmental stages of *H. contortus* were able to reduce FLU, with adult females being the most metabolically active. The larvae (L1/2 and L3) and adult females of the R-isolate reduced FLU more effectively than those of a S-isolate (Rychlá et al., 2024).

At least 68 genes encode SDRs in *C. elegans*, of which 63 have documented mRNAs. The importance of certain SDRs in nematode development and growth has been previously described (Maeda et al., 2001; Kamath et al., 2003; Simmer et al., 2003). In dauers (an alternative developmental stage, whereby the larva enters a type of stasis and can survive harsh conditions) the upregulation of 29 genes encoding SDRs was observed (McElwee et al., 2004). In the *H. contortus* genome, 46 members of the SDR superfamily were identified, mostly with a typical cofactor binding site motif (TGxxxGxG) (Šterbová et al., 2023). A comparison of SDRs expression among the developmental stages of this parasite, revealed great differences, which may indicate that individual SDRs perform distinct functions during the life cycle. Significant differences in the relative expression of these genes were also observed between S- and R-isolates of *H. contortus*. Moreover, some of SDR genes were inducible by the exposure of nematodes to sub-lethal doses of FLU. These results may indicate the potential participation of SDRs in the development of drug resistance in *H. contortus*.

Concerning AKRs, 17 and 22 genes were found in the genomes of *C. elegans* and *H. contortus*, respectively. A comparison of the expression of AKRs across the developmental stages and sexes of *H. contortus* revealed significant variations, where *akr-1*, *akr-3*, *akr-8*, and *akr-10* exhibited the highest level of expression. A phylogenetic analysis revealed that most AKR genes in *H. contortus* lack an orthologue in the sheep genome, which is a favorable finding for the consideration of AKRs as a potential drug target. In adults of a R-isolate, three AKRs were upregulated and seven AKRs were downregulated in comparison to S-isolate. In adults of a S-isolate, the exposure to FLU resulted in the induction of three AKR genes (Šterbová et al., 2024).

In contrast to SDRs and AKRs, only 13 MDR members have been found in *C. elegans* genome (Nordling et al., 2002) and no information about these enzymes in parasitic nematodes has been made available to

date.

4.4. Hydrolases of xenobiotics in nematodes

Hydrolases catalyze the cleavage of compounds with the participation of the water. In addition to numerous hydrolytic reactions of endogenous metabolism, hydrolysis also belongs to the phase I of xenobiotic biotransformation. Particularly, the cleavage of esters, amides, and epoxides is very common in mammals (Wang et al., 2018). In *C. elegans*, the hydrolysis of two xenobiotics, dichlorvos and nitrophenylacetate by carboxylesterase has been described (Kisan et al., 2015). Significant upregulation of carboxylesterase expression was observed in *C. elegans* exposed to fluoranthene, clofibrate, atrazine and β -naphthoflavone (Reichert and Menzel, 2005). Although humans express four epoxide hydrolase isoforms, *C. elegans* possesses only two isoforms, *ceeh-1* and *ceeh-2*, both of which exhibit endobiotic and xenobiotic metabolizing activities (Hartman et al., 2021).

The hydrolysis of acetanilide was studied in the nematode *A. lumbricoides/sum*, and it was found that the hydrolytic activity occurred in the cytosol of the intestinal epithelium and to a lesser extent in the cytosol of the reproductive organs, while cuticle and mesenchyme fluid showed no measurable activity (Douch and Gahagan, 1977). In *H. contortus*, the anthelmintic drug candidate BLK127 underwent hydrolysis of the amide group. The same reaction of BLK127 was observed in ovine liver (Zajíčková et al., 2022). The hydrolysis of nitrile represents one of the biotransformation reactions of the anthelmintic drug MPTL in *H. contortus*. Interestingly, this transformation of MPTL does not occur in ovine liver, which illustrates the nematode-specific nature of xenobiotic biotransformation (Stuchlíková et al., 2014). Nevertheless, nothing is known about the responsible hydrolytic enzyme(s).

On the contrary, in fluke *F. hepatica* carboxylesterases have been intensively studied due to their participation in the deactivation of anthelmintic drug triclabendazole with a potential role in triclabendazole resistance in this helminth (Scarcella et al., 2012; Pedroza-Gomez et al., 2021; Miranda-Miranda et al., 2023).

5. Phase II biotransformation enzymes

5.1. UDP-glycosyltransferases

UDP-glycosyltransferases (UGTs) constitute a large family of enzymes that facilitate the conjugation of compounds with UDP-activated sugar, a process that occurs in the majority of organisms. Their endogenous functions include growth regulation, protection against pathogens and abiotic stresses, and adaptation to changing environments (Gharabli et al., 2023). Moreover, their participation in the second phase of xenobiotic biotransformation plays a pivotal role in the defense mechanisms of various organisms. In general, the substrate specificity of drug-metabolizing enzymes, including UGTs, is broad, allowing them to metabolize a wide range of xenobiotic substrates (Lethe et al., 2024).

UGTs have been studied for their potential value in biomedical and environmental applications, including their use in crop protection (Gharabli et al., 2023). Moreover, UGTs are very interesting enzymes with regard to their involvement in xenobiotic resistance, particularly in the context of non-target site resistance mechanisms (Dimunová et al., 2022a). For instance, the overexpression of UGTs in weeds may result in resistance to herbicides with diverse modes of action and worsen the response to other compounds (Wrzesinska-Krupa et al., 2023). The involvement of UGTs in drug resistance is dependent on the manner of the drug detoxification, if glycoside formation is involved, UGTs' contribution to the resistance mechanisms warrants further investigation. In addition, UGTs may represent promising candidates as drug targets, as the inhibition of drug detoxification could prolong the efficacy of the drug.

In nematodes, UGTs belong to the most important xenobiotic-metabolizing enzymes as evidenced by the involvement of BxUGT16

in the detoxification of various nematocidal substances in the pine wood nematode *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* (Cao et al., 2023). As mentioned above, glycosylation of anthelmintics is a common phenomenon observed in nematodes (Table 2). In *H. contortus*, UGTs were comprehensively described, and their potential involvement in ABZ resistance was confirmed at multiple levels. Some genes exhibited elevated constitutive expression in a R-isolate throughout the entire life cycle (Matoušková et al., 2018; Kellerová et al., 2020a). Furthermore, the inducibility of UGTs by ABZ (Stasiuk et al., 2019; Kellerová et al., 2020b; Dimunová et al., 2022b), and increased glycosylation of ABZ in R-isolates provides additional evidence for UGTs involvement in the resistance mechanisms (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018; Kellerová et al., 2020b). Surprisingly, despite the absence of IVM glycosylation in *H. contortus* (Vokrál et al., 2013), UGTs have been identified among the differentially expressed genes in adults of the IVM-resistant strain, along with numerous other detoxification genes (Tuersong et al., 2023). Specifically, *UGT10B* (HCON_00127,680) was found to be upregulated in IVM-resistant males (Tuersong et al., 2023), as it was upregulated in the juvenile stages (eggs and L1) (Kellerová et al., 2020a), and was induced by ABZ and ABZSO in adult females of the benzimidazole-resistant strain (Kellerová et al., 2020b). All of these indicate the potential significance of this gene in the IVM-resistance mechanisms, although its role may be indirect and not directly related to IVM detoxification. The second upregulated gene in the IVM-resistant strain was *UGT371A1* (HCON_00108,700), a gene that has been reported on multiple occasions in the context of benzimidazole resistance in *H. contortus* (Kellerová et al., 2020b; Dimunová et al., 2022b). On the other hand, seven UGT genes were downregulated following *in vitro* exposure of *Parascaris univalens* to three anthelmintics from different classes, IVM, pyrantel citrate (PYR), and TBZ (Martin et al., 2020).

It is noteworthy that the commonly employed model organism for investigating nematode drug metabolism and resistance mechanisms, *C. elegans*, exhibited somewhat divergent results when compared to parasites. For example, the biotransformation products of benzimidazoles involve numerous glucose conjugates, likewise observed in *H. contortus* (Laing et al., 2010; Stasiuk et al., 2019). However, response to exposure to anthelmintics differs; e.g. 4 h of benzimidazole exposure caused an increased expression of eight UGT genes in *C. elegans*, but no transcriptional response in *H. contortus* (Stasiuk et al., 2019). The IVM exposure resulted in the differential expression of 1085 genes in *P. univalens* (including a down-regulated *ugt-54*) but expression of 15 orthologous genes in *C. elegans* remained unchanged, despite the dose-dependent behavioral effects observed (Dube et al., 2022). This indicates that the xenobiotic response in free-living *C. elegans* may significantly diverge from that observed in parasitic nematodes that reside in the host, which represent the target stage of the majority of drugs.

5.2. Glutathione S-transferases

The most well-known function of glutathione-S-transferase (GST) as a part of the second phase of xenobiotic metabolism is to catalyze an addition of a glutathione (GSH) to an electrophilic substrate. The formation of glutathione thioesters, which may undergo further catabolic reactions, ensures that the toxicity of xenobiotics is reduced. In addition, GSTs also help to overcome oxidative stress (OS) of various origins. Besides the host immune response, several new anthelmintics as well as some classes of conventional drugs induce OS resulting in damage to biomolecules (Nayak et al., 2012; Saini et al., 2014). In blood-feeding nematodes, there is an additional risk of OS induction by Fe²⁺ in free haem due to haemoglobin degradation (Wei et al., 2016). GSTs are inducible by OS (Nayak et al., 2012) as well as by xenobiotics (Polak et al., 2022; Stryński et al., 2024).

Given the obvious drawbacks for studying parasite physiology, pivotal data on nematode GSTs have been obtained from *C. elegans*. Increased *gst* expression following ROS exposure (Wu et al., 2015) and

the shortened lifespan of *gst* *C. elegans* knockdowns (Leiers et al., 2003; Ayyadevara et al., 2007) suggests a crucial role for GSTs in OS protection in this species. Furthermore, *C. elegans* is used as an expression model to study the role of proteins originally from parasitic nematodes – here too, GSTs were observed to protect against OS (Kampkötter et al., 2003).

In parasitic nematodes, increased enzymatic activity of GST has been described in *H. contortus* adults from R-isolates (Kawalek et al., 1984). In contrast, GST protein was downregulated in a R-isolate of *H. contortus* compared to a S-isolate (Tan et al., 2020). Increased GST activity in *H. contortus* eggs was associated with tolerance to TBZ (Kerboeuf and Aycardi, 1999). However, adults showed decreased GST activity after benzimidazole treatment due to a mechanism of action unrelated to OS induction (Tan et al., 2020).

In recent studies, upregulation of GST at both transcriptomic and proteomic levels was described in L3 larvae of the susceptible strain of *H. contortus* after IVM treatment (Liu et al., 2023). However, no significant up- or down-regulation of GST transcription level following *in vitro* IVM treatment was observed in adults of a R-isolate of *Teladorsagia circumcincta* (Dicker et al., 2011). The inhibition of GST in *A. lumbricoides/suum* L3 larvae lowered their viability and improved efficacy of both LEV and IVM (Hansen et al., 2016), suggesting both important role of GST in larval fitness and potential role in anthelmintic efficacy, although conjugation of any anthelmintics with GSH has not yet been observed in nematodes.

Nevertheless, GSTs are moonlight proteins, providing several other vital functions such as nutrition (Liebau et al., 1997; Xie et al., 2015), modulation of host cells (Jin et al., 2019; Piaggi et al., 2021), or prostaglandin synthesis (Joachim and Ruttkowski, 2011). As such, they are a vital part of the physiological development and fitness of parasitic nematodes (Joachim et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2021). Therefore, GST represents an appropriate candidate for the development of vaccines against nematode infections (Yadav et al., 2011; Diemert et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2017; Xiong et al., 2023).

The differences in the sequence and structure of filarial and human GSTs (Liebau et al., 1996, 1997; Sureshan et al., 2024), in addition to its crucial role as an antioxidant enzyme (Pemberton and Barrett, 1989), make GST supreme drug and vaccine target for human and cattle filarioses. A number of potential antifilarial drugs has been observed to interact with the filarial GST (Yadav et al., 2010; Mathew et al., 2011; Azeez et al., 2012) inhibiting its enzymatic activity (Sureshan et al., 2024) and thus lowering the viability of both micro- and macrofilariae (Kalani et al., 2014).

5.3. Other conjugation enzymes in nematodes

Sulfation or sulfonation is an essential and ubiquitous conjugation reaction that modifies a wide range of xenobiotic and endogenous molecules. Sulfotransferases relocate a sulfuryl group (SO₂) from the highly activated donor, 3'-phosphoadenosine 5'-phosphosulfate (PAPS), to the hydroxyl or amino group of numerous compounds. The binding of the charged sulfate group changes the physicochemical properties and biological activity of the acceptor molecules. Sulfation, thus represents a critical biomolecule modification, playing a major role in homeostasis, development and morphogenesis (Souhei et al., 2009). In eukaryotes, cytosolic and membrane-bound sulfotransferases are present. Cytosolic sulfotransferases (designated SULTs) sulfate xenobiotics and small molecules like neurotransmitters and hormones. Membrane-bound sulfotransferases are located in the Golgi complex and mediate the post-translational sulfation of endogenous macromolecules (proteins, lipids and glycosaminoglycans) (Igreja and Sommer, 2022).

In the genome of *C. elegans*, *ssu-1* (suppressor of stomatin mutant uncoordination) is the only member of the cytosolic sulfotransferase gene family. Orthologous proteins include the human SULT1B1, SULT2A1 and SULT2B1 enzymes. High levels of *ssu-1* expression were observed at both the embryonic and adult stages with even more enhanced in dauer larvae. The recombinant protein, named ceST1,

showed sulfation activity for several xenobiotic substrates such as 4-nitrophenol, 2-naphthol, and bisphenol A, but did not catalyze the sulfation of either monoamines or hydroxysteroids. These findings suggested that this sulfotransferase contributes to defense against xenobiotics (Hattori et al., 2006). A later study revealed that this sulfotransferase antagonizes insulin-like signaling to regulate and promote developmental arrest in response to osmotic stress in *C. elegans* (Burton et al., 2018). Nine paralogs of *C. elegans* *ssu-1* are found in the related nematode *Pristionchus pacificus*, and eight paralogs in parasitic nematode *Strongyloides ratti*. However, their biological role remains unknown (Igreja and Sommer, 2022).

Certain molecules with nitrogen in their structure can be conjugated with an acetyl group. N-acetyltransferases (NATs), working with acetyl-CoA as a coenzyme, are enzymes responsible for the acetylation of various endogenous and xenobiotic aliphatic amines, arylamines and heterocyclic amines, including drugs and carcinogenic compounds. NAT and NAT-like genes have also been identified in invertebrates, including several nematodes (Rodrigues-Lima and Dupret, 2002). NAT of the parasitic nematode *Ascaridia galli* catalyzes the acetylation of octopamine. High levels of NAT were found in the gonads of male and female worms and in the muscle/body wall (Muimo and Isaac, 1993). NAT activities towards p-aminobenzoic acid and 2-aminofluorene as substrates have been reported in *Anisakis simplex* (Chung et al., 1996), N-acetylation of 2-aminofluorene has also been detected in *Enterobius vermicularis* *in vitro* (Chung, 1999). *H. contortus* adults formed an acetylated metabolite of FLU (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018). Recombinant NAT from *C. elegans* catalyzed the N-acetylation of thialysine [S-(2-aminoethyl)-L-cysteine] (Abo-Dalo et al., 2004).

Methylation, using S-adenosylmethionine as the methyl group donor, is a common and very important reaction in all organisms, including nematodes. Many types of methyltransferases occur in their genome, but they are principally involved in methylation of endogenous substrates (e.g. DNA, phosphoethanolamine, peptides, glycans). The only report of the methylation of xenobiotics in nematodes was the detection of methylated metabolites of FLU in *H. contortus* adults *ex vivo* (Raisová Stuchlíková et al., 2018).

However, methylation of xenobiotics is more commonly reported in other helminths (such as *Hymenolepis diminuta*, *Dicrocoelium dendriticum*) (Cvilink et al., 2009b; Bártíková et al., 2012).

6. Conclusions and future perspectives

Many of the studies mentioned above clearly demonstrate that increased expression/activity of certain biotransformation enzymes could increase the tolerance of nematodes to certain anthelmintics. Increased constitutive expression of biotransformation enzymes in R-isolates compared to S-isolates has been repeatedly reported. Moreover, exposure of nematodes to sublethal doses of some anthelmintics resulted in induction of selected biotransformation enzymes and increased deactivation of the anthelmintic drug in subsequent therapy. However, most of the information has been obtained in *C. elegans* and *H. contortus*, and other nematodes have rarely been studied. In addition, the reasons for the constitutively increased expression and the mechanisms responsible for the induction have not yet been determined. Our understanding of the regulation of expression of biotransformation enzymes in nematodes is currently limited.

In general, the expression of genes involved in drug detoxification is under the control of a few ligand-activated transcription factors and nuclear hormone receptors (NHRs), referred to as xenosensors, which are also present in nematodes (Taubert et al., 2011; Ménez et al., 2019; Du et al., 2024). Some NHRs are activated by various xenobiotics (e.g. pollutants, drugs or dietary compounds) which leads to their binding to response elements located on the promoters of target genes, thereby modulating their expression.

Besides transcriptional factors, epigenetic regulation of gene expression, may also be involved. Epigenetic modifications, such as

histone modifications and DNA methylation, play a crucial role in the regulation of important cellular processes, such as gene expression and cellular differentiation, and have also been identified as key factors in various diseases. In humans, for example, the relationship between DNA methylation and the tissue-specific expression of *UGT1A10* (Oda et al., 2014), and the developmental regulation of *UGT1A1* expression via histone modifications have been reported. Conversely, in parasitic nematodes, information on the epigenetic regulation of biotransformation enzymes is still lacking.

Thus, the mechanism of induction of anthelmintic biotransformation enzymes is largely unknown, and it is also unknown whether the anthelmintic-induced changes in expression can be permanent, i.e. whether they are heritable and transferable to subsequent generations. Heritability of the enhanced expression of certain biotransformation enzymes induced by low doses of anthelmintics could explain the mechanism of the drug resistance development due to contact of nematodes with anthelmintic traces in the environment. However, this needs to be further studied.

Taken together, detailed knowledge of the biotransformation pathway of each anthelmintic in different nematode species and more information on biotransformation enzymes, their inducibility and regulation may be of value in limiting the development of resistance to new anthelmintics in advance (Haenlein and Park, 2020; Keiser, 2023).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ondřej Vosála: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Josef Krátký:** Writing – original draft, Data curation. **Petra Matoušková:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Nikola Rychlá:** Writing – original draft, Data curation. **Karolína Štěrbová:** Writing – original draft, Data curation. **Lucie Raisová Stuchlíková:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Data curation. **Ivan Vokřál:** Writing – original draft, Data curation. **Lenka Skálová:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Lenka Skalova reports was provided by Charles University Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Kralove. Lenka Skalova reports a relationship with Charles University that includes: employment. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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